

FEATURES OF TEACHING SOCIAL MEDICINE, PUBLIC HEALTH UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF THE STATE OF MARTIAL

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Abstract

Active hostilities throughout the territory of Ukraine, which have been ongoing since February 24, 2022 as a result of the aggression of the Russian Federation, have given rise to a number of problems in the field of higher education, one of which is ensuring the stability and continuity of the educational process. It was established that the peculiarity of the state of the territory in relation to the course of military operations began to play a key role both for those who teach (universities) and for those who are studying.

Keywords: educational process, martial law, distance learning.

The educational process in a medical university has always been different in its specificity, because it combines the theoretical component and the development of practical skills. After mastering basic disciplines in the first to third years, students of medical faculties study clinical disciplines for the next three years. Social medicine, public health is one of the few theoretical disciplines that is studied in senior courses and in the conditions of a sustainable educational process according to the curriculum; this is ensured by the presence of students in practical classes.

From 05:30 on February 24, 2022, [1] martial law was introduced in Ukraine - a special legal regime introduced in the event of armed aggression or threat of attack, danger to the state independence of Ukraine [2]. From that moment, our country was in a state of war due to the military aggression of the Russian Federation. In this regard, all spheres of activity, including education, had to adapt to functioning in new conditions. The introduction of martial law in Ukraine made significant adjustments not only in everyday life, but also in all areas of the socio-economic sector, making them militarily adapted [3]. The significant autonomy of the educational institution, ensured by the Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education", allows timely and dynamic adaptation of the educational process to the conditions of today [4]. We already had the opportunity to see this for ourselves during the coronavirus pandemic, when higher education institutions switched to distance or mixed forms of education. It is thanks to the work gained during the last two years under this work schedule that the university can now ensure the implementation of the educational program. Distance or mixed forms of education in the conditions of martial law have become not an alternative, but a production necessity.

A full-scale military invasion with the occupation of part of the regions and regular aerial bombardment of the entire territory of Ukraine caused the forced displacement of residents not only within the borders of the state, but also outside it. Therefore, not only students, but also the educational and teaching staff have changed their place of residence partially, and in some universities, completely. Under these circumstances,

remote support of the educational process will depend only on the availability of online access to the Internet, which is usually available in the territory where active hostilities are not conducted. This approach will make it possible to preserve personnel potential, communication with students, and most importantly, to ensure maximum safety of its participants.

With the introduction of martial law, the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine adopted a number of decisions to settle issues related to the organization of the educational process, in particular, higher education institutions were recommended to temporarily stop the educational process and go on vacation [5]. At the beginning of March, the management conducted a survey among the students about the readiness to start their studies, among the surveyed 56% of the students were safe and ready to start their studies. From March 15, 2022, by order of the university administration, the educational process in the distance format was resumed at the Bukovinian State Medical University.

It should be emphasized that the scientific and pedagogical staff of the department and students of 2-4 courses already had the experience of distance learning during the pandemic of the corona virus infection COVID-19, at the same time, 76% of students liked distance learning, at that time 48% of students considered saving time as the biggest advantage for commuting, 25% noted that distance learning provides more free time for training and personal affairs, 20% noted that studying at home is convenient, for 8% of respondents, this form of study made it possible to learn more information and find independent work. Distance education, according to the majority (80%) of the students, encouraged them because the teachers used modern technologies for teaching lectures and seminar classes with the help of services with support for video conferences "Zoom", "Google Meet", "Discord", provided educational methodological material, including textbooks, manuals, methodological recommendations and presentations in electronic form with 24-hour access, created documents for general use on the Google Classroom platform and in the distance learning system of the Bukovinian State Medical University "Moodle",

which allowed for effective processing of the material academic disciplines and pass online testing for control. Communication with teachers in messengers ("Telegram", "Viber", "WhatsApp", etc.) and the creation of communities of academic groups, departments, faculties made it easier to establish communication between students and teachers [6].

The survey of education seekers after the resumption of the educational process in the conditions of martial law showed that they consider the individualization of education, the flexibility of the study schedule in choosing the most convenient conditions (place and time), and the processing of theoretical material on various online platforms to be the most important opportunities of online education. In their opinion, the lack of necessary equipment at home and the lack of constant access to the Internet have a negative impact on the organization of full distance learning. More than 70% of students were able to start classes.

In the process of teaching under martial law, the teachers of the department of social medicine and the organization of health care use all forms of conducting educational classes (distance format: synchronous – video conferences if the necessary conditions are present; asynchronous format – methodical materials from the disciplines are placed on the Moodle platform, which applicants can use on your own All teachers have created chats to communicate with students (and subject groups) on Viber and/or Telegram messengers.

Among the main difficulties that arise during teaching under martial law, teachers note the lack of Internet for them and students, the escalation of hostilities, being in bomb shelters during classes.

Activities carried out by scientific and pedagogical staff of the department of social medicine and health care organizations with the aim of attracting students of higher education to attend educational classes:

- personal communication with each candidate for specialization (telephone conversations, correspondence in messengers and via e-mail);
- communication with heads of academic groups;
- creation of chats about disciplines in Viber and/or Telegram;
- communication of teachers with deans, deputy deans and methodologists of dean's offices;
- individual counseling of students who do not have the opportunity to attend classes online for technical and other reasons.

The analysis of the current success rate of students in the disciplines taught at the Department of Social Medicine and Public Health showed that the average test scores of future doctors were 70–82 points, which indicates a satisfactory level of acquired knowledge, and at the end of the academic year average success scores were 77–80 points, which makes it possible to talk about the success of the educational process at the department of social medicine and health care organization.

Conclusion. Thus, the generalization of the obtained data makes it possible to talk about the high-quality organization of the educational process during the period of martial law at the department of social medicine and the organization of health care, which is possible thanks to the combination of successful and coordinated activities of the administration of the academy and the staff of the department.

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